

Supplementary Material

Supplement table 1. The inter- and intra-assay coefficients of variation of the included biomarkers

Biomarker	Coefficients of variation (%)
ft3	4.75
ft4	6.01
TT3	5.97
TT4	4.43
TSH	2.98
Tg	4.08
HCG	7.05
TPOAb	
45.17 IU/mL	4.79
110.66 IU/mL	3.69
TgAb	
65.06 IU/mL	5.40
201.71 IU/mL	2.48
521.35 IU/mL	2.17
TSH receptor antibody	
4.05 IU/L	6.69
16.45 IU/L	4.13

TSH, thyroid stimulating hormone; ft4, free thyroxine; ft3, free triiodothyronine; Tg, thyroglobulin; TPOAb, thyroperoxidase antibodies; TgAb, thyroglobulin antibodies; HCG, Human chorionic gonadotropin.

Supplemental table 2. Regression coefficients and standard error of determinants and their association to thyroid function in multivariable regression models. N = 795

	TSH		FT4		FT3 ^c	
	$\beta \pm SE$	P value	$\beta \pm SE$	P value	$\beta \pm SE$	P value
Maternal age, years	0.014±0.010	0.156	-0.004±0.001	0.015	-0.002±0.001	0.114
Parity; para 1 or more	0.118±0.082	0.151	0.016±0.012	0.179	0.003±0.009	0.715
Body mass index, kg/m ²	-0.006±0.012	0.629	-0.003±0.002	0.127	0.002±0.001	0.065
WAMI index ^a	0.104±0.260	0.691	0.078±0.038	0.043	0.024±0.028	0.395
Fetal sex; female ^b	-0.123±0.069	0.077	0.018±0.010	0.076	0.002±0.008	0.740
Gestational age, weeks ^c	0.060±0.012	0.000	-0.010±0.002	0.000	0.000±0.001	0.884

TSH, thyroid stimulating hormone; FT4, free thyroxine; FT3, free triiodothyronine; WAMI, Water/sanitation, Assets, Maternal education, and Income. Natural log-transformed values of FT4 and FT3 were used in the regression models. Missing information on ^a1, ^b33, and ^c4 participants. Estimates are adjusted for TSH-receptor antibodies, thyroperoxidase antibodies, thyroglobulin antibodies. ^cIn addition estimates are in this model adjusted for Human chorionic gonadotropin.

Supplemental table 3. Regression coefficients and standard error of determinants and their association to thyroid function in multivariable regression models. N = 795

	TT3		TT4	
	$\beta \pm SE$	P value	$\beta \pm SE$	P value
Maternal age, years	-0.001±0.001	0.475	-0.354±0.168	0.036
Parity; para 1 or more	-0.013±0.010	0.193	0.914±1.376	0.507
Body mass index, kg/m ²	0.006±0.001	0.000	-0.064±0.203	0.751
WAMI index ^a	0.018±0.032	0.571	-2.951±4.384	0.501
Fetal sex; female ^b	-0.006±0.009	0.517	1.556±1.175	0.186
Gestational age, weeks ^c	0.014±0.002	0.000	1.843±0.226	0.000

TT3, total triiodothyronine; TT4, total thyroxine; TSH, thyroid stimulating hormone; WAMI, Water/sanitation, Assets, Maternal education, and Income. Natural log-transformed values of TT3 were used in the regression model. Missing information on ^a1, ^b33, and ^c4 participants. Estimates are adjusted for TSH-receptor antibodies, thyroperoxidase antibodies, thyroglobulin antibodies, and Human chorionic gonadotropin.

Supplemental table 4. Regression coefficients and standard error of determinants and their association to thyroid antibodies in multivariable regression models. N = 795

	Thyroperoxidase Antibodies ^d		TSH-receptor Antibodies ^e		Thyroglobulin antibodies ^d	
	$\beta \pm SE$	P value	$\beta \pm SE$	P value	$\beta \pm SE$	P value
Maternal age, years	0.020±0.014	0.145	0.000±0.002	0.949	-0.004±0.013	0.779
Parity; para 1 or more	0.001±0.111	0.990	0.007±0.015	0.634	0.025±0.103	0.811
Body mass index, kg/m ²	-0.016±0.016	0.335	0.002±0.002	0.498	0.001±0.015	0.947
WAMI index ^a	0.146±0.351	0.678	-0.031±0.049	0.534	0.462±0.327	0.158
Fetal sex; female ^b	0.002±0.094	0.984	0.007±0.013	0.587	-0.027±0.088	0.759
Gestational age, weeks ^c	-0.030±0.018	0.102	-0.004±0.003	0.118	-0.010±0.017	0.549

TSH, thyroid stimulating hormone; WAMI, Water/sanitation, Assets, Maternal education, and Income. Natural log-transformed values of thyroperoxidase antibodies, TSH-receptor antibodies, and thyroglobulin antibodies were used in the regression models. Missing information on ^a1, ^b33, and ^c4 participants. ^dEstimates are adjusted for Human chorionic gonadotropin. ^eEstimates are adjusted for Human chorionic gonadotropin, thyroperoxidase antibodies, and thyroglobulin antibodies.

Supplemental Figure A. The associations between possible determinants and concentrations of free triiodothyronine (FT3) with corresponding 95% confidence intervals. The plots are based on multiple linear regression using natural log-transformed values. The model is adjusted for maternal age, gestational age, parity, body mass index, fetal sex, WAMI index, TSH-receptor antibodies, thyroperoxidase antibodies, thyroglobulin antibodies, and Human chorionic gonadotropin. N=795, missing information on one participant for WAMI index, four participants for gestational age, and 33 participants on fetal sex.

Supplemental Figure B. The associations between possible determinants and concentrations of total triiodothyronine (TT3) with corresponding 95% confidence intervals. The plots are based on multiple linear regression using natural log-transformed values. The model is adjusted for maternal age, gestational age, parity, body mass index, fetal sex, WAMI index, TSH-receptor antibodies, thyroperoxidase antibodies, thyroglobulin antibodies, and Human chorionic gonadotropin. N=795, missing information on one participant for WAMI index, four participants for gestational age, and 33 participants on fetal sex.

Supplemental Figure C. The associations between possible determinants and concentrations of total tetraiodothyronine (TT4) with corresponding 95% confidence intervals. The plots are based on multiple linear regression where the model is adjusted for maternal age, gestational age, parity, body mass index, fetal sex, WAMI index, TSH-receptor antibodies, thyroperoxidase antibodies, and thyroglobulin antibodies. N=795, missing information on one participant for WAMI index, four participants for gestational age, and 33 participants on fetal sex.

Supplemental Figure D. The associations between possible determinants and concentrations of thyroperoxidase (TPO) antibodies with corresponding 95% confidence intervals. The plots are based on multiple linear regression using natural log-transformed values. The model is adjusted for maternal age, gestational age, parity, body mass index, fetal sex, WAMI index, and Human chorionic gonadotropin. N=795, missing information on one participant for WAMI index, four participants for gestational age, and 33 participants on fetal sex.

Supplemental Figure E. The associations between possible determinants and concentrations of thyroglobulin (TG) antibodies, with corresponding 95% confidence intervals. The plots are based on multiple linear regression using natural log-transformed values. The model is adjusted for maternal age, gestational age, parity, body mass index, fetal sex, WAMI index, and Human chorionic gonadotropin. N=795, missing information on one participant for WAMI index, four participants for gestational age, and 33 participants on fetal sex.